

$L_2^e(\mathbb{T}^2)$ FAZODA DISKRET SHREDINGER OPERATORI XOS QIYMATI

Jumayeva Guljahon Akmalovna
jumayevaguljahon725@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ishda muhim spektr turg'unligi haqidagi Veyl teoremasi, to'rt noma'lumli tenglamalar sistemasiga mos $\Delta^e(z)$ determinant, formula orqali aniqlangan H chiziqli, chegaralangan va o'z-o'ziga qoshma operator tahlil keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: teorema, lemma, determinant, operator, uchburchakli panjara, formula, isbot.

$L_2^e(\mathbb{T}^2)$ orqali $\mathbb{T}^2 = (-\pi, \pi]^2$ da aniqlangan, kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi barcha juft funksiyalar fazosini belgilaymiz. Uchburchakli panjarada aniqlangan diskret Shredinger operatori $L_2^e(\mathbb{T}^2) \rightarrow L_2^e(\mathbb{T}^2)$ fazoda quyidagi formula orqali aniqlanadi [1]:

$$H = H_0 - V, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $H_0 - \varepsilon(x)$ funksiyaga ko'paytirish operatori, ya'ni

$$(H_0 f)(x) = \varepsilon(x)f(x),$$

V esa

$$(Vf)(x) = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} v(x, p)f(p)dp$$

ko'rinishda aniqlangan integral operator, bunda

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon(x) &= -\frac{1}{3}(\cos x_1 + \cos x_2 + \cos(x_1 - x_2)), \\ v(x, p) &= \mu_1 + \mu_2 \cos x_1 \cos p_1 + \mu_2 \cos x_2 \cos p_2 + \\ &\quad + \mu_3 \cos(x_1 - x_2) \cos(p_1 - p_2). \end{aligned}$$

Eslatib o'tish joizki, (1) formula orqali aniqlangan H chiziqli, chegaralangan va o'z-o'ziga qo'shma operator bo'ladi.

Muhim spektr turg'unligi haqidagi Veyl [2] teoremasiga asosan H operatorning $\sigma_{ess}(H)$ muhim spektri kompakt V qo'zg'alishda o'zgarmaydi va qo'zg'almas H_0 operatorning spektri $\sigma(H_0)$ bilan ustma-ust tushadi. Shunday qilib, $\sigma_{ess}(H)$ muhim spektr $\varepsilon(s)$ funksiyaning qiymatlar to'plamidan iborat bo'ladi [3], ya'ni

$$\sigma_{ess}(H) = \sigma(H_0) = [m, M], \quad m = \min(\varepsilon(s)) = -1, \quad M = \max(\varepsilon(s)) = \frac{1}{2}$$

V operatorning musbat ekanligidan, quyidagilarni hosil qilamiz:

$$\sup(Hf, f) \leq \sup(H_0 f, f) = M(f, f).$$

Bu yerdan va $\sup \sigma(H) = \sup_{\|f\|=1} (Hf, f)$ tenglikdan H operator, muhim spektrdan

o'ngda xos qiymatga ega bo'la olmaydi.

Teorema. Ixtiyoriy $z < -1$ uchun shunday $\mu_0 > 0$ topilib, $\mu_0 = \mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3$ bo'lganda z soni H operatorning xos qiymati bo'ladi.

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$\Delta^o(z) = \begin{vmatrix} \mu_1 A - 1 & \mu_2 B & \mu_2 B & \mu_3 C \\ \mu_1 B & \mu_2 D - 1 & \mu_2 E & \mu_3 F \\ \mu_1 B & \mu_2 E & \mu_2 D - 1 & \mu_3 F \\ \mu_1 C & \mu_2 F & \mu_2 F & \mu_3 G - 1 \end{vmatrix}, \quad z < -1$$

$$A = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$B = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$C = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$D = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$E = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$F = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

$$G = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}$$

Teoremani isbotlash uchun quyidagi lemmadan foydalanamiz:

Lemma. $z < -1$ soni H operatorning xos qiymati bo'lishi uchun $\Delta(z) = 0$ bo'lishi zarur va yetarli.

Lemma isboti: Faraz qilaylik z xos qiymat bo'lsin, ya'ni

$$(Hf)(x_1, x_2) = zf(x_1, x_2)$$

yoki

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{3}(\cos x_1 + \cos x_2 + \cos(x_1 - x_2))f(x_1, x_2) - \mu_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2) \\ & - \mu_2 \cos x_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_1 f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2) \\ & - \mu_2 \cos x_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_2 f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2) \\ & - \mu_3 \cos(x_1 - x_2) \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos(p_1 - p_2) f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2) \\ & = zf(x_1, x_2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$a = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$b = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_1 f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$c = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_2 f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$d = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos(p_1 - p_2) f(p_1, p_2) d(p_1, p_2)$$

U holda (2) tenglama ushbu ko'rinishni oladi:

$\varepsilon(x_1, x_2)f(x_1, x_2) - \mu_1 a - \mu_2 b \cos x_1 - \mu_2 c \cos x_2 - \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2) = z f(x_1, x_2)$
 $z \notin \left[-1, \frac{1}{2}\right]$ bo'lganligidan $\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z \neq 0$ kelib chiqadi. U holda

$$f(x_1, x_2) = \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} \quad (3)$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. (3) ni a, b, c, d ifodalarni integral qiymatiga qo'yamiz

$$a = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$b = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_1 \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$c = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos p_2 \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} d(p_1, p_2)$$

$$d = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \cos(p_1 - p_2) \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} d(p_1, p_2)$$

Bundan quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasiga kelamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(-1 + \mu_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} \right) a + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} b + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} c \\ & + \mu_3 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} d = 0 \\ & \mu_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} a + \left(-1 + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} \right) b + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} c \\ & + \mu_3 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} d = 0 \\ & \mu_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} a + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} b + \left(-1 + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} \right) c \\ & + \mu_3 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} d = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu_1 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} a + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} b \\ & + \mu_2 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_2 \cos(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} c + \left(-1 + \mu_3 \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2(p_1 - p_2) dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} \right) d \\ & = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Yuqoridagi belgilashlardan (4) tenglamalar sistemasi quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} (\mu_1 A - 1)a + \mu_2 Bb + \mu_2 Bc + \mu_3 Cd = 0 \\ \mu_1 Ba + (\mu_2 D - 1)b + \mu_2 Ec + \mu_3 Fd = 0 \\ \mu_1 Ba + \mu_2 Eb + (\mu_3 D - 1)c + \mu_3 Fd = 0 \\ \mu_1 Ca + \mu_2 Fb + \mu_2 Fc + (\mu_3 G - 1)d = 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Bu 4 noma'lumli tenglamalar sistemasiga mos $\Delta^e(z)$ determinantni tuzamiz:

$$\Delta^e(z) = \begin{vmatrix} \mu_1 A - 1 & \mu_2 B & \mu_2 B & \mu_3 C \\ \mu_1 B & \mu_2 D - 1 & \mu_2 E & \mu_3 F \\ \mu_1 B & \mu_2 E & \mu_2 D - 1 & \mu_3 F \\ \mu_1 C & \mu_2 F & \mu_2 F & \mu_3 G - 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

(3) ga ko'ra $(a, b, c) \neq (0, 0, 0)$, (5) sistema noldan farqli yechimga ega bo'lishi uchun $\Delta^e(z) = 0$ bo'lishi zarur.

Yetariligi. $\Delta^e(z) = 0$ bo'lsin, u holda (5) sistema $(a, b, c) \neq (0, 0, 0)$ yechimga ega bo'ladi. Quyidagicha funksiyani qaraymiz

$$g(x_1, x_2) = \frac{\mu_1 a + \mu_2 b \cos x_1 + \mu_2 c \cos x_2 + \mu_3 d \cos(x_1 - x_2)}{\varepsilon(x_1, x_2) - z} \quad (6)$$

Tekshirib ko'rish mumkinki, $(Hg)(x_1, x_2) = zg(x_1, x_2)$ bo'ladi. Demak, z H operatorning xos qiymati, (6) esa H operatorning xos funksiyasi bo'ladi Lemma isbotlandi.

Teoremani isbotlash uchun z ning xos qiymat bo'lishi uchun zarur va yetarli shartlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Bu shartlar determinant sistemaning yechimlari va integral ifodalar orqali ifodalanadi. Olingan xos funksiyalar shakli aniq ifodalanadi va ular operator tenglamasini qanoatlantirishi ko'rsatiladi.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, agar determinant sharti bajarilsa, H operatorida asosiy spektrdan tashqari xos qiymatlar bo'lishi mumkin. Bu qiymatlar potensial funksiyalar va integral yadroning tuzilishiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Teorema isboti : Faraz qilaylik $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu$ bo'lsin, u holda $\Delta^e(z)$ quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi

$$\Delta^e(z) = \begin{vmatrix} \mu A - 1 & \mu B & \mu B & \mu C \\ \mu B & \mu D - 1 & \mu E & \mu F \\ \mu B & \mu E & \mu D - 1 & \mu F \\ \mu C & \mu F & \mu F & \mu G - 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantni birinchi ustun bo'yicha yoyamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta^e(z) &= (\mu A - 1) \begin{vmatrix} \mu D - 1 & \mu E & \mu F \\ \mu E & \mu D - 1 & \mu F \\ \mu F & \mu F & \mu G - 1 \end{vmatrix} - \mu B \begin{vmatrix} \mu B & \mu B & \mu C \\ \mu E & \mu D - 1 & \mu F \\ \mu F & \mu F & \mu G - 1 \end{vmatrix} \\ &+ \mu B \begin{vmatrix} \mu B & \mu B & \mu C \\ \mu D - 1 & \mu E & \mu F \\ \mu F & \mu F & \mu G - 1 \end{vmatrix} - \mu C \begin{vmatrix} \mu B & \mu B & \mu C \\ \mu D - 1 & \mu E & \mu F \\ \mu E & \mu D - 1 & \mu F \end{vmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Hisoblashlarni bajarganimizdan so'ng tenglikning o'ng tomonidan quyidagi umumiy ko'paytuvchi qavs oldiga chiqadi:

$$\Delta^e(z) = (\mu E - \mu D + 1)((\mu A - 1)[2(\mu F)^2 - (\mu G - 1)(\mu E + \mu D - 1)] + 2\mu B[\mu B(\mu G - 1) - \mu C\mu F] - \mu C[2\mu B\mu F - \mu C(\mu E + \mu D - 1)])$$

$\Delta^e(z)=0$ bo'lishi uchun $\mu E - \mu D + 1 = 0$ ekanligini ko'rsatamiz.

$$\mu(D - E) = 1$$

$$D = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} > 0,$$

$$E = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z},$$

Koshi-Bunyakovskiy formulasiga ko'ra:

$$E = \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos p_1 \cos p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} \leq \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}} \sqrt{\int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_2 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z}}$$

$$= \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\cos^2 p_1 dp_1 dp_2}{\varepsilon(p_1, p_2) - z} = D,$$

Demak, $D - E > 0$, $\mu = \frac{1}{D-E} > 0$ bo'ladi.

Agar $\mu = \frac{1}{D-E}$ deb olsak, u holda $\Delta^e(z) = 0$ bo'ladi. Bu esa 2-lemmaga ko'ra $z < -1$ soni H operatorning xos qiymati bo'lishini anglatadi. Teorema isbotlandi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

- [1] K. Ando, I. Hiroshi, H. Hisashi, "Spectral properties of Schrödinger operators on perturbed lattices", Ann. Henri Poincaré, 17, 2103 (2016).
- [2] M. Reed, B. Simon, Methods of Modern Mathematical Physics, Vol. 4, Analysis of Operators, Academic Press, London, 1980.
- [3] M. Muminov, J. Pardaev, "The Spectrum of Discrete Schrödinger Operator on a Three Dimensional Triangular Lattice with a Finite-range Potential", Lobachevskii Journal of Mathematics, Vol. 45, No. 4, pp. 1722–1728, 2024.